

SYNTHESES IN THE ACRIDINE SERIES. PART III.
N-SUBSTITUTED 4-METHOXY-7-CHLORO-9-AMINOACRIDINE

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A number of N-substituted 4-methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridines (wherein both OMe and Cl have been shifted to 4 and 7 positions respectively) has been synthesised; the 9-substituted groups being dialkylamino-alkylamine, aromatic and heterocyclic amino groupings and some simple substituents like OH and COOH

We have already described the synthesis of a number of chloromethoxy-9-dialkyl-aminoacridines (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 224, 466), wherein the chlorine atom at position 6 and the methoxy group at position 2 (as present in the atebirin molecule) have been transferred to those at 5 and 4 respectively, while keeping the other fixed at its original position. In the present paper we have described the syntheses of a number of N-substituted 4-methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridines, wherein both the methoxy group and chlorine atom have been shifted to positions 4 and 7 respectively. The various substituents at position 9 include certain dialkylamino-alkylamines of the type present in atebirin, some heterocyclic and aromatic amino groupings and some simple substituents like hydroxy and carboxyl. 4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridine has been prepared and condensed with *p*-acetylaminobenzene sulphonyl chloride.

2:5-Dichlorobenzoic acid has been condensed with *o*-anisidine to give 6'-methoxydiphenylamine-4-chloro-2-carboxylic acid, which on treatment with POCl₃ gives 4-methoxy-7:9-dichloroacridine. This is condensed with various amino compounds in the usual way. During the condensation of 4-methoxy-7:9-dichloroacridine with some simple amino compounds like ethanolamine, urethane, piperazine, and ethylenediamine, the acridine is converted quantitatively into the corresponding acridone and no condensation product could be isolated. This difficulty has been overcome and the desired compounds are obtained through the acid chloride. In general, the route to the compounds of atebirin type also, through the diphenylamine-*o*-carboxylamide, is extremely convenient one, the reaction proceeding very smoothly with good yields. No acridones are obtained. The intermediate amides could be isolated in a number of cases, but have not been done so, except in the case of condensation with ethanolamine.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

6'-Methoxy-4-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic Acid.—After a number of preliminary experiments varying the solvents and temperature etc. the following conditions were found to give the best results. A mixture of potassium salt of 2:5-dichlorobenzoic acid (22.9 g., 1 mol.), *o*-anisidine (18.4 g., 1.5 mol.), precipitated copper (0.2 g.) and cuprous chloride (0.2 g.) was refluxed with *isoamyl* alcohol (30 c.c.) for 2 hours. Steam was passed into the reaction mixture, which removed all the *isoamyl* alcohol and any unreacted *o*-anisidine. The residue was boiled with sodium bicarbonate (10. g.) (charcoal) and filtered. On decomposition with hydrochloric acid, a greenish yellow product was obtained. Another reprecipitation through the potassium salt gave the product in yellow form, yield 60%. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in glistening pale yellow needles, m. p. 200-1°. (Found : N, 4.98. $C_{14}H_{12}O_3NCl$ requires N, 5.04 per cent).

6'-Methoxy-4-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxyl chloride was obtained in the usual way by treating the diphenylamine acid with PCl_5 (1 : 1 mol. ratio), using absolute petroleum ether (40-60°) as the reaction medium. It was crystallised from light petroleum ether in yellow needles, m.p. 101°. (Found : N, 4.70. $C_{14}H_{11}O_2NCl$ requires N, 4.73 per cent).

4-Methoxy-7 : 9-dichloroacridine.—**6'-Methoxy-4-chlorodiphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid** (5 g) was refluxed with phosphoryl chloride (35 c.c.) at 130° for 4 hours. After removing excess of phosphorus oxychloride under vacuum, the brownish residue was cooled externally in ice and treated with excess of ice-cold ammonia solution. A yellow product was obtained which was thoroughly triturated with ammonia solution and then dried in a vacuum desiccator. It was crystallised from absolute benzene in golden yellow needles, m.p. 183-84°, yield 76%. (Found : N, 5.10. $C_{14}H_9O NCl_2$ requires N, 5.03 per cent). This acridine is fairly unstable and hydrolyses to the corresponding acridone, after being left exposed for about 72 hours. The change occurs even in a sealed tube after some time. After crystallisation it was immediately used for condensation.

Compounds Nos. 1-7 were prepared according to the general procedure (I), 8 to 20 according to procedure (II), and those numbering 21 to 24, according to procedure (III).

(1) **4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(γ -diethylaminopropyl)aminoacridine** (*General Procedure I*).—A mixture of 4-methoxy-7:9-dichloroacridine (2.78 g., 1 mol.) dissolved in phenol (10 g.) and γ -diethylaminopropylamine (1.3 g., 1 mol.) was heated at 100° for 3 hours. After cooling, it was diluted with 100 c.c. of ether and phenol was removed by washing with 2*N*-sodium hydroxide solution. The ethereal extract was then treated with dilute acetic acid (30 c.c.), when the base passed to the aqueous layer.

Ether was removed and the acetate was decomposed with alkali and the base taken up in ether. After drying over fused potassium carbonate, the dihydrochloride was precipitated by the addition of alcoholic hydrogen chloride. It was crystallised from a mixture of absolute ethanol and ether as a deep yellow powder, m.p. 205-07° (decomp.). It is soluble in water and in alcohol. (Found : N, 9.32. $C_{21}H_{20}ON_3Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 9.44 per cent).

(2). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(δ -diethylaminobutyl) aminoacridine dihydrochloride* was crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and ether as a deep yellow powder, m.p. 210-12° (decomp.). It is soluble in water. (Found : N, 9.25. $C_{22}H_{25}ON_3Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 9.16 per cent).

(3) *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(ϵ -diethylaminoamyl) aminoacridine dihydrochloride* was crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and ether as a deep yellow powder, m.p. 204° (decomp.). It is soluble in water. (Found : N, 8.62. $C_{23}H_{30}ON_3Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 8.89 per cent).

(4) *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(γ -di-n-propylaminopropyl) aminoacridine*.—The dihydrochloride was twice crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and ether as a yellow powder. It forms a hydrate, m.p. 114-120°. After drying in an air-oven at 100° for 4 hours, the melting point was raised to 206-08° (decomp.). (Found for anhydrous substance) : N, 8.59. $C_{23}H_{30}ON_3Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 8.88 per cent).

(5). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(γ -di-n-butylaminopropyl) aminoacridine*.—The dihydrochloride was crystallised thrice from a mixture of absolute alcohol and ether as a yellow powder with solvent of crystallisation, m.p. 134-37°. The hydrate is very stable and could not be converted into the anhydrous compound even by heating at 125° for several hours under high vacuum. The hydrate was boiled with absolute alcohol for 20 minutes and excess of alcohol was then slowly evaporated on a water-bath, until a yellow powder separated. It was filtered and dried in a vacuum desiccator, m.p. 292-94° (decomp.), darkening at 250°. [Found (in the anhydrous substance) : N, 8.22. $C_{25}H_{34}ON_3Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 8.39 per cent].

(6) *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(γ -di-n-anylaminopropyl) aminoacridine*.—The dihydrochloride was thrice crystallised from absolute alcohol and ether mixture as a yellow powder. It forms a very stable hydrate which could not be converted into the anhydrous compound. It shrinks at 110° and melts at about 145°, solidifies again and then melts above 200° with decomposition. It is quite soluble in water. For analysis the meconate was prepared by treating the dry ethereal extract of the base with meconic acid dissolved in ether. A yellow powder separated, which was thoroughly washed with ether and crystallised from absolute alcohol, m.p. 205° (decomp.). (Found : N, 6.25. $C_{27}H_{38}ON_3Cl$, $C_7H_4O_7$ requires N, 6.40 per cent).

(7). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(γ -piperidinopropyl) aminoacridine dihydrochloride* was crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and ether in a deep yellow powder, m.p. 233-35° (decomp.). (Found : N, 9.28. $C_{22}H_{28}ON_3Cl$, 2HCl requires N, 9.20 per cent).

- (8). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(4'-methoxyphenyl) aminoacridine*: (Procedure II).—Chloroacridine (0.5 g., 1 mol.) was dissolved in phenol (4 g.) *p*-Anisidine (0.24 g., 1.1 mols) was added and the mixture heated at 100-110° for 2 hours. After cooling, the reaction mixture was diluted with 20 c.c. of ether, when the hydrochloride separated out. It was thoroughly washed with ether and crystallised from absolute alcohol as orange-yellow, slender needles, m.p. 248-50° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7.20. $C_{21}H_{17}O_2N_2$, HCl requires N, 6.98 per cent). To obtain the free base, the hydrochloride was warmed with 2*N*-NaOH solution and after trituration was filtered and washed and crystallised from dilute alcohol as orange coloured needles, m.p. 165-67°.
- (9). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(4'-methylphenyl) aminoacridine*—The hydrochloride was crystallised from absolute alcohol in orange-yellow needles, m.p. 260°. (Found: N, 6.96. $C_{21}H_{17}ON_2Cl$, HCl requires N, 7.27 per cent). The free base was crystallised from dilute alcohol as orange glistening needles, m.p. 225-27°.
- (10). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(4'-ethoxyphenyl) aminoacridine*.—The hydrochloride was crystallised from alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 258-59° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.77. $C_{22}H_{19}O_2N_2Cl$, HCl requires N, 6.74 per cent).
- (11). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(4'-acetaminophenyl) aminoacridine*.—The free base was crystallised from absolute alcohol in orange-red needles, m.p. 263-64°. (Found: N, 10.95. $C_{22}H_{15}O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 11.10 per cent).
- (12). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(α -naphthyl) aminoacridine*.—The hydrochloride was crystallised from absolute methyl alcohol as orange needles, m.p. 261-62° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.82. $C_{24}H_{17}ON_2Cl$, HCl requires N, 6.65 per cent).
- (13). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(carboxymethyl) aminoacridine*.—The condensation of 4-methoxy-7:9-dichloroacridine with glycine was carried out as described above. The product obtained was dissolved in 5% sodium hydroxide and decomposed with hydrochloric acid. Another precipitation was carried out with dilute acetic acid. The product was crystallised from 70% methyl alcohol as greenish yellow needles, m.p. 237-39°. (Found: N, 8.78. $C_{16}H_{15}O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 8.84 per cent).
- (14). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(4'-carboxyphenyl) aminoacridine* was purified through its sodium salt as in the above case. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol as an orange-yellow powder, m.p. 277-78° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7.10. $C_{21}H_{13}O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 7.37 per cent).
- (15). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(2'-dimethylaminophenyl) aminoacridine*.—The free acridine base was crystallised from absolute alcohol as orange-red crystals, m.p. 204-5°. (Found: N, 10.95. $C_{22}H_{20}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 11.05 per cent).
- (16). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(4'-dimethylaminophenyl) aminoacridine*.—The free base was twice crystallised from absolute alcohol as an orange, microcrystalline powder, m.p. 256-58° (decomp.). (Found: N, 11.40. $C_{22}H_{20}ON_2Cl$ requires N 11.12 per cent).

- (17). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(4'-diethylaminophenyl) aminoacridine*.—The base was crystallised from absolute alcohol as scarlet, slender needles, m.p. 223-25° (decomp.). (Found: N, 10.59. $C_{24}H_{24}ON_3Cl$ requires N, 10.35 per cent).
- (18). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(cyclohexyl) aminoacridine*.—The hydrochloride was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in greenish yellow needles, m.p. 312-13° (decomp.). (Found: N, 7.68. $C_{20}H_{21}ON_2Cl$, HCl requires N, 7.42 per cent).
- (19). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(p'-sulphanilaminophenyl) aminoacridine*.—The free base was crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and methyl alcohol, m.p. 272-74° (decomp.) with previous darkening at 260°. (Found: N, 10.01. $C_{20}H_{16}O_3N_3ClB$ requires N, 10.15 per cent).
- (20). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(p'-arsenophenyl) aminoacridine* was purified by decomposition of its sparingly soluble sodium salt with dilute acetic acid and was crystallised from methyl alcohol as an orange powder. It shrinks a little at 210° and melts with decomposition at 220-22°. (Found: N, 6.11. $C_{20}H_{16}O_4N_2ClAs$ requires N, 6.10 per cent).
- (21). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(piperidino) acridine*.—The chloroacridine (0.5 g.), phenol (4 g.) and piperidine (0.2 g) were heated in a sealed tube at 100° for 3 hours. After cooling, the mixture was poured into excess of 2*N*-sodium hydroxide. The yellow product obtained after trituration was filtered, and washed with water. It was crystallised from absolute alcohol as greenish yellow needles, m.p. 237-39°. (Found: N, 8.45. $C_{19}H_{19}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 8.57 per cent).
- (22). *6'-Methoxy-4-chlorodiphenylamine-2-(β-hydroxyethyl) amide*: (*General Procedure III*).—A mixture of 6'-methoxy-4-chlorodiphenylamine-2- carboxyl chloride (2.96 g., 1 mol.) in absolute benzene (20 c.c.) and ethanol amine (0.61g., 1 mol.) was warmed on a water-bath for 10 minutes, when the yellow colour disappeared. On cooling, a white product separated, which was filtered and washed with dilute ammonia. It was crystallised from alcohol as white, microcrystalline, slender needles, m. p. 141-42°. (Found: N, 8.58. $C_{16}H_{17}O_3N_3Cl$ requires N, 8.73 per cent).
- (23). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(β-hydroxyethyl) aminoacridine*.—After treatment of the acid chloride with ethanolamine as described above, benzene was removed under vacuum and the residual semi-solid mass refluxed with phosphoryl chloride (6 c.c.) for 2 hours after which the unused phosphoryl chloride was removed under vacuum. The yellow residue was decomposed with dilute ammonia with cooling and the product so obtained was crystallised from dilute alcohol as golden yellow slender needles, m.p. 172-74°. (Found: N, 9.15. $C_{16}H_{17}O_2N_2Cl$ requires N, 9.26 per cent).
- (24). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(carboethoxy) aminoacridine* was obtained through the acid chloride by condensation with urethane. The base obtained was crystallised from ethyl acetate as golden yellow needles, m.p. 188-90°. (Found: N, 8.20. $C_{17}H_{15}O_3N_2Cl$ requires N, 8.47 per cent).

(25). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(piperidino)acridine* was obtained as above by condensation with piperazine (more than 2 mols.). It was crystallised from a mixture of absolute alcohol and ethyl acetate as golden yellow, slender needles, m.p. 190-92°. (Found : N, 12.62. $C_{18}H_{18}ON_3Cl$ requires N, 12.82 per cent).

(26). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(β -aminoethyl) aminoacridine* was obtained by the condensation of the acid chloride with excess of ethylenediamine as described above. It was crystallised from absolute ethanol as stout, yellow crystals, m.p. 172-74°. (Found : N, 13.75. $C_{16}H_{11}ON_3Cl$ requires N, 13.93 per cent).

(27). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridine*.—*4-Methoxy-7 : 9-dichloroacridine* (2 g.) was dissolved in phenol (12 g.) at 80° and treated slowly with ammonium carbonate (2.5 g.). After the addition was complete, the temperature was raised to 130° and maintained for 20 minutes. After cooling, ether (100 c.c.) was added and the hydrochloride precipitated by passing dry hydrogen chloride. It was washed with ether and acetone. It is fairly soluble in water, from which it crystallises as a yellow powder, m.p. 290-92° (decomp.) with previous darkening at 270°. The free base obtained by the decomposition of the hydrochloride was crystallised from dilute alcohol as yellow needles, m.p. 235-37°. It is quite soluble in acetone. (Found : N, 10.71. $C_{14}H_{11}ON_2Cl$ requires N, 10.83 per cent).

(28). *4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-(p'-acetylaminophenylsulphonyl) aminoacridine*.—*4-Methoxy-7-chloro-9-aminoacridine* (2 g., 1 mol.) was dissolved in dry pyridine (20 c.c.). *p*-Acetylamino benzene sulphonyl chloride (2 g., 1.5 mols.) was added slowly. A yellow powder began to separate immediately. After leaving overnight, the product was filtered and washed with dry ether. It was crystallised from a large volume of pyridine as glistening yellow crystals, m.p. 282-83° (decomp.). (Found : N 9.11. $C_{22}H_{18}O_4N_3ClS$ requires N, 9.22 per cent).

4-Methoxy-7-chloroacridone.—The chloroacridine (0.4 g.) was refluxed with hydrochloric acid (5% 30 c.c.) for 10 minutes. The white acridone that separated, after drying was crystallised from glacial acetic acid as white needles, m.p. 294-95°. (Found : N, 5.51. $C_{14}H_{10}O_2NCl$ requires N, 5.39 per cent).

The acridone was also obtained by cyclisation of 6'-methoxy-4-chloro-diphenylamine-2-carboxylic acid with concentrated sulphuric acid.

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